

Deliverable 5.1

Detailed requirements and (non-) technical specifications for all services based on the user consultations

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Deliverable n°	1
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1. Summary

Based on user surveys a non-technical description has been compiled to describe the services to build. For each subtask (5.1, 5.2, 5.3) an independent software requirement specification is presented in this document. The three specifications will be merged for the implementation. This process is envisaged to remove redundancies and find synergies, like common user authentication, email notification systems, etc. and highlight dependencies to other packages like user embargo for unpublished results, accounting etc.

1.1. Scope of task 5.1:

Here we present a detailed description of the homeless data portal and the underlying RI specific tools for data curation, QC and archiving of data. Furthermore, the document will present the features and interface of the application, what the application will do, as well as constraints related to RI specific tools and workflows. The document is intended for stakeholders in the projects, developers, and users of the application.

1.2. Scope of task 5.2:

This service will provide air mass origin information to analyse atmospheric in situ based observations from fixed and mobile observation platforms. Users will get access to state-of-the-art Lagrangian Particle Dispersion Models (LPDM), where they can start on-demand calculations by specifying the geographical coordinates of receptor points and time of interest.

1.3. Scope of task 5.3:

The purpose of this document is to present the system requirements of the time series analysis service that will be implemented in the frame of the ATMO-ACCESS Task 5.3. Furthermore, the document will present the features and interface of the application, what the application will do, as well as constraints related to RI specific tools and workflows. The document is intended for stakeholders in the projects, developers, and users of the application.

More information on the ATMO-ACCESS project can be found [here](#).

1.4. Common references

ATMO-ACCESS	https://www.atmo-access.eu/
IAGOS	https://www.iagos.org/
ICOS	https://www.icos-cp.eu/about
ACTRIS	https://www.actris.eu/about
STILT	http://stilt-model.org/index.php/Main/HomePage
FLEXPART	https://www.flexpart.eu/

2. Deliverable 5.1 - Task 5.1: Development of online tools for data curation of homeless data

2.1. Introduction

Homeless Data: Data resulting from research campaigns and TNA activities are normally not included into any data management and data curation system and activity. These data sets are “homeless data”, not associated with any long-term projects nor sustainable data centres. The objective of this task is to develop tools facilitating access to TNA data and campaign data for future use through long term, sustainable data centres”

2.1.1. Intended Audience and Reading Suggestions

- Programmers who will work on developing the software.
- Stakeholder who will need to validate the requirements, making sure they fulfil what is in the project description.
- Researchers who have or will perform TNA activities or campaign measurements.

2.1.2. Product Scope

The Homeless data portal is set up to serve scientists producing atmospheric measurements and time series resulting from research campaigns and TNA activities that are normally not included into any data management and data curation system and activity. These data sets are “homeless data”, not associated with any long-term projects nor sustainable data centres. The objective of this task is to develop tools facilitating access to TNA data and campaign data for future use through long term, sustainable data centres. The goal of the tool is to make more data available to the end-user, as well as benefits for data collectors in terms of usage tracking and access to RI specific tools for curation and data access.

The Homeless data portal is not a QA tool, but an archiving and access tool to data that is currently not curated anywhere today. The goal is to document the homeless data through rich meta data to document quality and provide access. This tool is for data that is not regularly produced within the RIs, but as an offer to research projects and TNA activities, making sure that also this data is available for future use.

2.2. Overall Description

2.2.1. Product Perspective

The homeless data portal will be developed for everyone collecting atmospheric composition data during TNA and campaign activities. The goal is to directly curate and store TNA and campaign datasets in long-term repositories. After curation the previously homeless data will be stored, published and made accessible through the existing ACTRIS, IAGOS or ICOS data repositories and respective portals.

The data will be subject only to a very simple consistency and quality check and will be published with clear metadata flags to inform the user that this data is not the same quality as the normal RI products.

The homeless data portal will be a simple form based one-page application. The form will prompt multiple questions that the data provider will need to answer to describe their data. Based on the description and metadata selected in the form, the application will automatically route the request to the relevant RI. If it is not clear from the answers in the form which RI the data belongs to, a combined effort will be made. All requests will end up in an issue tracking system, where tasks are delegated to data curators at the specific RIs.

In addition, it should be possible for the different RIs, to connect their specific data curation workflows to the API of the issue tracking systems, in cases where it is possible to automate parts of the data curation process. A more detailed explanation of RI specific workflows is available in Chapter 2.4.2.

Figure 1 Homeless data portal overview

2.2.2. Product Functions

2.2.2.1. User View

- Form:

- Open the website, fill in form with PI information and information describing the dataset or collection of dataset from TNA and/or campaign activities.
- Feedback:
 - User will receive an email confirmation and a link to the issue tracking system.
- Issue tracking system:
 - Open issue tracking system, see "tickets" associated to a specific user, as well as the status.

2.2.2.2. *System View*

- Form:
 - Form information is stored and metadata from form selection is provided to the API of the issue tracking system.
- Workflows:
 - Depending on the selected parameters and other relevant metadata from the "Homeless data portal" form, different workflows will be triggered in the issue tracking system.
 - Form will trigger storage of data in those cases where the data provider wants to provide examples or send the whole dataset together with the form metadata.
 - If a file is provided, the file will be saved to a secondary archive, to ensure backup and traceability.
- Feedback
 - Issue tracking system will be "in-charge" of sending feedback upon creation and update of a specific issue.
 - Feedback to the data provider from any step in the data curation workflow at each RI, should be provided through the centralized issue tracking system.

2.2.2.3. *Research Infrastructure (RI) View*

- RI will look through the request for providing data and accept/decline in the issue tracking system.
- RI will provide all feedback through the issue tracking system.
- It should be possible for RI to utilize issue tracking API for integrating the data curation process with their internal workflow and data curation tools.

2.2.3. User Classes and Characteristics

Multiple type of users, not only users who are internal to the RIs. It can be users from both free external research projects, in addition to ATMO-ACCESS TNA. For example:

- Researchers, data providers and technical staff that are part of campaigns and TNA activities.
- Data curators at each RI

- Developers who is working on the project and further developing the functionality

2.2.4. Operating Environment

Browser based application, should work on all operating systems and across the most used web-browsers.

2.2.5. Design and Implementation Constraints

The first version of the requirements specification will not include any specific information on design and implementation. This will be handled in MS5.2 (Mockups of services presented to user panels) and MS5.3 (Prototype services presented to user panels).

2.2.6. User Documentation

User documentation will be created when the prototype of the portal is operational (estimated on 1st October 2022).

2.2.7. Assumptions and Dependencies

The application will run in the browser, and therefore it will not require any specific dependencies to run.

2.3. External Interface Requirements

2.3.1. User Interfaces

Details of the user interface design will be documented in a separate user interface specification (MS 5.2).

2.3.2. Software Interfaces

The "Homeless data portal" will need to connect to the issue tracking system through an API. The "Homeless data portal" will need to connect to a secondary storage system through an API.

2.4. System Features

2.4.1. Interactive form

Form elements

All elements should be multiple choice, so it would be possible to specify metadata for a collection of datasets

1. Atmospheric component(s) you are working with
 - Aerosol
 - Greenhouse gases
 - Reactive trace gases
 - Clouds

- Other
- 2. Observation type
 - Ground based In-Situ observations
 - Ground based Remote sensing observations
 - Aircraft measurements (remote or in-situ)
 - Other mobile/moving platforms (remote or in-situ)
 - Other, please specify
- 3. What specific kind of measurement data do you want to submit and archive for long term access?
 - Gas concentrations/mixing ratio: Greenhouse gases (CO₂, CH₄, N₂O)
 - Gas concentrations/mixing ratio: Greenhouse gases (halocarbons and other fluorinated gases)
 - Gas concentrations/mixing ratio: Reactive trace gases (VOC, NO_x, ozone, CO)
 - Aerosol properties: Ground based In-Situ aerosol optical, physical and chemical properties
 - Aerosol properties: Remote observations from ground – profiles
 - Aerosol properties: Remote observations from ground – total column
 - Cloud properties: Ground based In-Situ measurements
 - Cloud properties: Ground based remote sensing observations – profiles
- 4. Location of measurements site(s)?
 - One country in Europe
 - Europe
 - Northern Hemisphere
 - Southern Hemisphere
 - Arctic regions
 - Antarctic region
 - Globally distributed
 - Asia
 - America
- 5. What is the nature of the data you would like to store?
 - Campaign data
 - Annual data
 - Other, please specify
- 6. Is your data currently formatted and undergoing certain quality assurance criteria, or unformatted/not quality assured?
 - Includes metadata and quality-controlled data for defined criteria (processed data)
 - Only partly include metadata or quality-controlled data for defined criteria

- Not formatted nor quality assured
- 7. Contact information
 - First name
 - Last name
 - Organization name
 - Country code
 - Delivery point
 - Address city
 - Administrative area
 - Postal code
 - Email
 - Position name
- 8. Attach a file or example of your data (optional)
- 9. Specific constraints
 - Embargo
 - Licencing etc.
- 10. Is this a collection of datasets.
 - Yes
 - No
- 11. Expected volume of the data
 - Provide file or size of collection in Megabytes

Other relevant information?

2.4.2. Workflows

2.4.2.1. *ACTRIS*

ACTRIS InSitu

Within ACTRIS, the data submission & curation process is tracked in an issue tracker to have traceable quality control. The issue status indicates where the submission is located in the process. The issue status also indicates who is responsible for the next step. Below the workflow description and figure describing the ACTRIS In Situ workflow is included.

Table 1 ACTRIS InSitu workflow description

Curation step	Status on this page	Responsibility	Task
called		The responsible submitter at the station / NF	A new data submission is expected by the station via the data submission tool , either because a new submission period started and you submitted data for the previous reporting period, or because a previous submission contained errors that require a re-submission. The responsible person at the station / NF needs to act.
curation	curation	Data Centre/EBAS team	The DC is conducting its QC procedures on the submission. The DC needs to act.
feedback	feedback	The responsible submitter at the station / NF	An issue with the submission needs to be resolved with an answer by the NF via the issue tracker. The NF needs to act.
closed - archived	closed - archived	No action required.	The issue is closed because the submission has been accepted and is published in EBAS.
closed - finally rejected	closed - finally rejected		The issue is closed because the it has been finally rejected and no re-submission is expected.
extQC	extQC (not implemented yet)	TC/Quality Control Centre/WCCAP	The submission undergoes QC at the TC (for those variables having QC review by the TC). The TC needs to act.
extQC feedback		The responsible submitter at the station / NF	Under QC review, the TC detected an issue, which needs to be resolved by an answer by the NF via the issue tracker. The NF needs to act.
extQC accepted		Data Centre/EBAS team	Under QC review, the TC has decided to accept the data submission. The submission can be processed further. The DC needs to act.
extQC rejected		Data Centre/EBAS team	Under QC review, the TC has decided to reject the submission. The DC will reject the submission without publishing it and call for a new submission. The DC needs to act.
	rejected		The file has been rejected. The related workflow might be in status 'called' or 'closed - finally rejected', or, after a new submission in any other state.

Figure 2 ACTRIS InSitu workflow

ACTRIS GRES

Figure 3 ACTRIS GRES workflow

2.4.2.2. IAGOS

Figure 4 IAGOS workflow

2.4.2.3. ICOS

Figure 5 ICOS workflow

2.5. Other Requirements

- Storage of data and metadata must follow GDPR requirements.
- This system aims to use a common login solution for authentication and authorization in WP5. The authentication and authorization should be done at a higher level, and the specific implementation is not to be considered as a part of this task.

3. Deliverable 5.1 - Task 5.2: Trajectory and Footprint services

3.1. Introduction

3.1.1. Intended Audience and Reading Suggestions

- Researchers who will use the service.
- Programmers who will work on developing the service.
- Stakeholders who will need to validate the requirements, making sure they fulfil what is in the project description.

3.1.2. Product Scope

This service will provide air mass origin information to analyse atmospheric in situ based observations from fixed and mobile observation platforms. Users will get access to state-of-the-art Lagrangian Particle Dispersion Models (LPDM), where they can start on-demand calculations by specifying the geographical coordinates of receptor points and time of interest. The model calculations will be hosted in virtual machines in the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and model output will be accessible from a data repository through open access and identified by a DOI. The atmospheric footprints will be convolved with a limited choice of different emission inventory data to allow analysis of concentrations and comparison with observation data from the data centres of the ACTRIS, IAGOS and ICOS research infrastructures. A user survey was conducted for an inclusive design approach. The survey aimed to clarify the users need and expectations and the results were considered in the presented software specification. The full transcript and analysis for each section is available in Appendix B: User survey for the ATMO ACCESS trajectory and footprint service.

The following services are being developed:

- Service connected to observation of greenhouse gases (using STILT and FLEXPART) @ ICOS
- Service connected to observation of aerosol components (using FLEXPART) @ ACTRIS. Reactive or depositing gases are in principle excluded unless the behaviour during transport can be modelled using a simple first order decay function.
- Service connected to observation of flight vertical profiles at airports (using FLEXPART) @ IAGOS

3.2. Overall Description

The following subsections contain a more detailed description of the services. The biggest challenge for the presented system and software requirements definition, is the decentralised nature of the services. Each service will run independently within the corresponding RI, but with a common interface and a minimal set of functionalities valid for all model runs in all services.

3.2.1. Product Perspective

A high-level description of the product, or in our case services are depicted in Fig 1. Here we explain the main use case, and a simplified workflow or guidance from request to result. The specific and detailed technical requirements for the implementation are described in the following sections.

From left to the right (1 to 7) the general workflow starts with the 'user' which can be a human or a machine and ends with the 'consumption' of the results by humans or machines. The midpart shows the interface between the different steps with the core (4) of three Research Infrastructures doing the computational work.

Figure 6: High level product perspective

1. Input or usage of the services may be by humans or machines. The main user group to start the process of new calculations is expected to come from a scientific background.
2. Human interface (website) where the user manually provides the necessary information to run the model.
3. A strict constraint set of information provided to the services to run the models. As depicted, input can arrive from humans, robots etc if the input conforms to the requirement. The submission shall be a simple https post statement.
4. Symbolic interface to the three Research Infrastructures. The idea is that the Ri's can implement independently their services, based on their expertise to set-up and run the model. From a user perspective this is a 'black box' returning model results, regardless where the computation takes place.

5. The model results from all RI's are accessible through a shared interface. It is not defined where the data physically is stored, but from a user's perspective this shall not be import.
6. Dissemination of the results for human through a website to provide facilities for search, visualisation, and data download.
7. Access to the results through API or http request or similar, such that machines or scripts may download the data automatically.

3.2.2. Product Functions

The following list should describe an exhaustive list of functions to cover the complete life cycle for input, validation, monitoring and dissemination. Since the implementation is likely to be split up to cater for the individual RI's, we have created three groups of functions. One is describing the Users view, one the overall system to 'glue' together the individual processes and one describes the RI's internal responsibilities.

3.2.2.1. *Users View*

- Open the website, fill out the form to provide necessary information, submit the form to the backend.
- Open the website, fill out the form to provide necessary information, save the form as JSON text file, can be used as template for automation.
- Provide login information for billing and statistics of data tracking
- Authorisation may be filled automatically if the users arrive from a different Service where the login already took place.

3.2.2.2. *System View*

- Input from website: JSON text file to submit for processing.
- Input from the website: JSON text file validation
 - o Validate input from user
 - o Validate authorization
 - o Provide feedback if station (TODO radius?) already exists, or for fixed stations, if results for a station within the same model grid cell and at the same height exist (TODO: define Backend action)
- Backend sends request to the Research Infrastructure for processing
- Backend creates a combined interface for all queuing systems
- Backend keeps a database to store:
 - o Which user has started which job?
 - o Keep user information
 - profile, password, login, email.... maybe only a UUID connected to an external authorization system
 - o Notify user if job is finished

- Backend checks regularly if a job takes abnormally (TODO: define time) long
- Backend provides a web interface to see an aggregation of all queues from the RI's
- Backend accepts automatic updates from the RIs about the queue
 - o Job started
 - o Job status
 - o Job finished (TODO, Parameters for billing, statistic need to be defined & implemented here)
- Backend provides a user aggregation to download results

3.2.2.3. *RI View*

- RI accepts request and starts new job in queue.
- RI provides feedback about queue.
- RI stores the results into the predefined storage
- RI provides UUID for results.
- RI stores metadata about the station
- RI provides a service to query metadata about existing results/stations/runs
 - o Geographical Info
 - o Spatial extent
 - o Temporal extent

3.2.3. User Classes and Characteristics

General methods to create the system include the following characteristics:

- User must be able to login, reset password, change profile information
- User must be able to start a new model run
- User must be able to view user queue / job started for each RI.
- User must be notified when the results are available
- User must be able to login, select result and either download or visualise results.
- User must be able to select and view results from other users as well.
 - o Depends on the accounting implemented and possible embargos.
 - o Dependency on other package for User AAI.

The following items describe the fields required in the json file submitted to the RI, provided from the user/machine.

Minimal input required by the Research Infrastructure to compute the footprints

- usage:
 - o authorisation token
 - o selected RI
 - o selected model

- o name
- o email (send notification when queue is finished?)
- input:
 - o latitude
 - o longitude
 - o elevation (receptor) height
 - o stations id
 - o stations name
 - o time start/end
 - o tracer
- configuration:
 - o tracer components (TODO: define a controlled list)
 - o aggregations (TODO: define a controlled list or methods)

3.2.4. Operating Environment

Since we will provide a demonstrator and it is not clear who runs the web services, ideally the services outside the Research Infrastructure are developed as a docker image(s). This would allow to scale, change, and distribute the services with a common place for development for all RI.

3.2.5. Design and Implementation Constraints

Currently unknown

3.2.6. User Documentation

For the footprints, the documentation and help should provide at least two categories to the user

- Handling of the overall system
 - o Where do I find the service?
 - o What does the service offer?
 - o What kind of data does the user need to provide
 - o Who is authorised to use the service?
- Description of the different models
 - o An example for the implementation of the STILT model at the ICOS Carbon Portal <https://www.icos-cp.eu/data-services/tools/stilt-footprint>
 - o Flexpart: <https://www.flexpart.eu/>
 - o Other Models?
 - o How to interpret the results
 - o Assumptions, constraints, uncertainties

3.2.7. Assumptions and Dependencies

To create this web service to calculate footprints (STILT & Flexpart) from three different RI's (IAGOS, ACTRIS, ICOS) the following prerequisites are identified:

- Each RI must provide a service to calculate footprints.
- Each RI provides storage to keep the results for dissemination.
- Each RI provides a UUID, PID or other similar persistent identification to access at least a permanent landing page including meta data with further information about the results and how to access the data.
- Each RI provides a system to download the results
- Each RI must provide contact details, for technical support (footprint calculations, queues, unfinished jobs, etc...)
- A system must be maintained to run the web service, database, etc. as described in System View. TODO:
 - o Who is responsible to run this service?
 - o Technical contact for the service?
 - o Long-term Support beyond the project duration?

Optional

- A virtual environment or web service is provided to disseminate the results. An example to visualise STILT footprints and timeseries can be found at <https://stilt.icos-cp.eu/viewer/>
- Another possibility to disseminate the results would be to use a Virtual Research Environment (like Jupyter Notebooks) for a more interactive user experience and possible synergies with Task 5.1 & 5.3.

3.3. External Interface Requirements

"A visualization of footprints and emissions as well as concentration time series in the footprint service is appreciated. 80% would prefer notification by e-mail after completion of the run."

3.3.1. User Interfaces

- Registration webpage
 - o <input>Username
 - o <input>Institute / Affiliation
 - o <input>ORCID
 - o <input>Password
- Login webpage

- Possible login with ORCID, if user provided in registration
- `<input>`Username
- `<input>`Password
- `<button>`Submit
- `<button>`Reset Password -> confirmation email if username exists
- `<button>`Register User -> webpage registration
- Run footprint service
 - `<input>` see different fields defined in '2.3 Input'
 - `<button>` Submit
- Notification Service
 - Email is sent to User
 - User can login to results page and [Download service] [VRE]
- Download service
 - Based on the notification received by the user (email? other method?), a list of results needs to be prepared for the user
 - `<input>`select from list
 - `<button>` download
- Virtual Research Environment
 - Load data from persistent identification
 - Predefined spatial and temporal visualisation (synergy to Task 5.3?)

3.3.2. Hardware Interfaces

No specific request, other than the hardware should be able to run a Unix/Linux Operating system to execute the proposed docker images.

3.3.3. Software Interfaces

Based on the assumption that docker images are developed as web services, a secure (https) web connection to the public is necessary.

3.3.4. Communications Interfaces

All communication between the different services and RIs shall be

- standard HTTPS GET/POST
- JSON notation for payload
- Require an authorization token (billing, statistics)

3.4. System Features

3.4.1. Interactive form

Mock-ups were not created yet, due to the expectation that the software requirement specification for Tasks 5.1, 5.2, 5.3 are merged to exploit synergies of common tasks, such as email notification, webserver hosting, etc.

3.4.2. Workflows

An overarching workflow is depicted in Section 2.1 Product Perspective but needs to be refined for the front-end user view, after merging the specifications from Task 5.1, 5.2, 5.3. Further a workflow needs to be defined within each RI but is out of scope for this document. Only the 'interface' and communication towards the RI is described here, but the description and implementation of the services is left to the RIs.

3.5. Other Non-functional Requirements

3.5.1. Safety and Security Requirements

As general rule to the ATMO Access Footprint services, the user (human or machine) must login to the services with a validated email address and affiliation. This validation may come from a different (3rd party) services, like ORCID or similar.

- The service shall adhere to the European GDPR rules.
- The service must provide access to the personal data.
- The service will store submitted jobs to calculate footprints from the different RIs and hence must provide access to this information.

The expectation is that an overarching AAI system is provided within ATMO access. To expedite the development of the described service we assume the requests arriving are legitimate.

4. Deliverable 5.1 - Task 5.3 Interactive time-series analysis

4.1. Introduction

4.1.1. Intended Audience and Reading Suggestions

- Programmers who will work on developing the service.
- Stakeholder who will need to validate the requirements, making sure they fulfil what is in the project description.
- Researchers who will use the service.

4.1.2. Product Scope

The product will provide users with:

- a unified access to long-term time series from the ACTRIS, IAGOS and ICOS Research Infrastructures,
- data filtering tools,
- tools for time series statistical analysis,
- tools for interactive data visualization,
- download of the data produced by the service and citation

A preliminary survey was conducted on user needs and requirements for the ATMO-ACCESS Interactive time-series analysis service. Parts of the results will be used in this document. Results of the survey are available in Appendix B.

4.2. Overall Description

4.2.1. Product Perspective

This product is an interactive online service aimed at instant exploration, analysis and visualization of level 2 data (final quality controlled observational data) from the ACTRIS, IAGOS and ICOS Research Infrastructures (see Fig. 7). The service will be built upon a dedicated library, which itself is a core part of the product and will be available to advanced users via a VRE (Virtual Research Environment).

Figure 7 The product from the user's perspective

4.2.2. Product Functions

- Browse and select time series data,
- Filter selected data based on a single or multiple criteria.
- Perform an exploratory analysis of the filtered data.
- Perform trend analysis of the filtered time series data.
- Visualize the filtered data.
- Perform user-defined calculations on the filtered data (in the VRE only).
- Download data:
 - the user can simply download the data
 - the user wants to cite the produced datasets and ask for a PID. He will then be automatically redirected to an external data curation system.

4.2.3. User Classes and Characteristics

There will be a unique class of users of the system. All users will have access to the same features.

4.2.4. Operating Environment

The product will be available in two forms:

- as a VRE (Virtual Research Environment) within which an advanced user will be able to autonomously work with the data by using the dedicated library (being the core

part of the product); this form will allow greater flexibility in comparison to the interactive online service;

- as an interactive online service running in the user's web browser.

Both should work on all operating systems and across the most commonly used web-browsers.

4.2.5. Design and Implementation Constraints

The first version of the requirements specification will not include any specific information on design and implementation. This will be handled in MS5.2 (Mockups of services presented to user panels) and MS5.3 (Prototype services presented to user panels).

The API of the dedicated library will be provided in a programming language widely used in scientific computing (e.g. python, R).

4.2.6. User Documentation

The user documentation will be provided in several forms, depending on a part of the product which is concerned:

- For a VRE version there will be:
 - an online API reference of the product's dedicated library
 - a repository with ready-to-use example scripts demonstrating possible use cases of the library.
- For an online interactive service there will be an online user guide.

4.2.7. Assumptions and Dependencies

The product will be fed with data from ACTRIS, IAGOS and ICOS research infrastructures. Data access will be provided by specific python libraries delivered by the RIs in the framework of ENVRI-FAIR. Each of the libraries implements a common data access interface (see <https://github.com/damienboulanger/envri-wp8-demonstrator> for details).

APIs could also provide access to datasets results of the Footprint service that will be implemented in Task 5.2.

4.3. External Interface Requirements

4.3.1. User Interfaces

Details of the user interface design will be documented in a separate user interface specification.

4.3.2. Hardware Interfaces

No extra hardware interfaces are needed.

4.3.3. Software Interfaces

- Data access libraries (with API's in python) provided by the RI's (see 2.7).

4.3.4. Communications Interfaces

The system will use HTTP protocol for communication with the web browser and the web server.

4.4. System Features

4.4.1. Interactive form

- Browse and select from available time series data, in particular containing data on:
 - o gas concentration / mole-fraction of
 - greenhouse gases (CO₂, CH₄, N₂O)
 - reactive trace gases (Ozone, CO, VOC, NO_x)
 - o aerosol properties:
 - ground based In-situ aerosol optical, physical and chemical properties
 - remote observations from ground (subject to data availability)
 - o cloud properties:
 - ground based In-situ measurements
 - ground based remote sensing observations (subject to data availability)
- Filter selected data based on a single or multiple criteria:
 - o spatial area (latitude-longitude extent or station name),
 - o temporal extent,
 - o time period (day/night; months or season),
 - o variable selection,
 - o altitude range,
 - o thresholds (min, max or both) for a selected variable.
- Exploratory analysis of the filtered time series data by calculating:
 - o Gaussian mean and standard deviation,
 - o moving average,
 - o percentiles (including min, max and median),
 - o autocorrelation.
- Trend analysis of the filtered time series data using
 - o linear fit method,
 - o non-parametric Mann-Kendall model,
 - o Theil-Sen slope estimate.
- Comparison of two (or more) variables using:
 - o linear regression,
 - o multiple lines on one plot,

- scatter plot,
- principal component analysis.
- Visualization of the filtered data (including scatter plot of individual data records, histograms, etc), of the above-mentioned statistics as well as 2d gridded statistics (averages, percentiles, etc.) if time series data has a spatial component (e.g. the data from IAGOS RI).
- Calculations on the filtered data defined by a user (available in the VRE only).
- Download of calculated data directly or via an external data curation system.

4.4.2. Workflows

Figure 8 The product from the system perspective

4.5. Other non-Functional Requirements

The tool will be interactive, and its results are supposed to be available to the users instantaneously. If necessary, a cache of the service's intermediate and/or results will be used in order to improve responsiveness of the service. The need for this caching system will be subject to results of technical tests.

4.6. Safety and Security Requirements

Users will have to authenticate to use the service. A common authentication system will be shared with Tasks 5.1 and 5.2. Authentication will secure the services and allow users to provide feedback on the services.

5. Glossary

AAI	Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure
ACTRIS	The Aerosol, Clouds and Trace Gases Research Infrastructure
API	Application Programming Interface
ENVRI	Environmental Research Infrastructures
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability
FLEXPART	Flexible Particle dispersion model
IAGOS	In-service Aircraft for a Global Observing System
ICOS	Integrated Carbon Observation System
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
PID	Persistent Identifier
RI	Research Infrastructure
STILT	The Stochastic Time-Inverted Lagrangian Transport model
VRE	Virtual Research Environment

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Appendix A: User Survey Task 5.1

https://git.nilu.no/atmo-access/task5.1-srs/-/blob/main/docs/user_survey_task5.1.pdf

Appendix B: User survey Task 5.2

This service will provide air mass origin information to analyse atmospheric in situ ground-based observations from fixed and mobile observation platforms. Users will get access to state-of-the-art Lagrangian Particle Dispersion Models (LPDM), where they can start on-demand calculations by specifying the geographical coordinates of receptor points and time of interest. The model calculations will be hosted in virtual machines in the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and model output will be accessible from a data repository through open access and identified by a DOI. The atmospheric footprints will be convolved with emission inventory data to allow analysis of concentrations and comparison with observation data from the data centres of the [ACTRIS](#), [IAGOS](#) and [ICOS](#) research infrastructures.

The following services are being developed:

- Service connected to observation of greenhouse gases (using STILT and FLEXPART)
- Service connected to observation of aerosol components (using FLEXPART)
- Service connected to observation of flight vertical profiles at airports (using FLEXPART)

STILT – Stochastic Time-Inverted Lagrangian Transport model

FLEXPART – FLEXible PARTicle dispersion model

ICOS on-demand STILT computation service for footprints and CO₂ concentration:

<https://www.icos-cp.eu/data-services/tools/stilt-footprint>

ACTRIS service offering visualization of pre-calculated FLEXPART footprints and aerosol (BC) concentration:

https://niflheim.nilu.no/NikolaosPY/Bely_2020_huang_cams.py

FLEXPART footprints are calculated operationally for observations in IAGOS, more information on Back Trajectories can be found here:

http://iagos-data.fr/ - CMSConsultPlace:ANCILLARY_DATA

The purpose of this survey is to identify the needs and expectations of potential users of the trajectory and footprint service. The data gathered will help to design the interface to the service, define the requirements for the model configurations and preferred access to model results.

The survey was anonymous, but participants had the chance to provide their e-mail address in case they are interested to be consulted again after the installation of the first prototype for their feedback and further requirements. 7 out of 20 participants are interested and provided their e-mail contact.

Survey participants

Most of the participants were closely related to one or more Research Infrastructures.

Is your research part of or closely related to existing Research infrastructures (RI)? If so, which ones are more interesting for you?

20 responses

Most of the participants were scientists, some responsible for measurement stations. Only two participants had also modelled expertise.

What is your role and expertise?

20 responses

Purpose

All participants plan to use the footprints for the interpretation of their measurements, mostly in hindcast, and 25% would also run the footprints for hypothetical stations to investigate new station locations. 25% are also interested to use the footprints for measurement campaign planning, which would require forecast capability of the footprint service.

What would your intended use of a footprint service be?

20 responses

Tracers

Considering the distribution of participants across the RIs they are equally interested in trace gases and aerosols as well as in surface/tall tower, profiles and flight tracks.

Which atmospheric components are most interesting for you?

20 responses

If you are interested in simulating concentrations of atmospheric tracers, which ones would be most interesting?

20 responses

If you are interested in simulating aerosol components, which ones would be most interesting?

13 responses

What kind of (model) data are you most interested in? Different data types require different model capabilities and settings.

20 responses

Emissions

In order to support further source attribution, all participants would like to get information on the GHG, and aerosol components split into emission regions and categories. Again, relative to the representation of RIs all types of emissions sources (surface, atmospheric) are equally important.

Should the GHG or aerosol be split into separate components - if feasible? What kind of component separation would be useful for you?

20 responses

What type of emission sources are interesting for you?

20 responses

Model set-up requirements

Most participants are interested in model simulation over Europe. With respect to the IAGOS community also global simulation will be needed.

What is your main geographical region of interest? Note that not all model configurations might be available for a region.

20 responses

Preferred minimum spatial resolution is $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$ with time resolution of 1-3 hours and time span of the simulation between episodes of a few days (also in forecast mode) and several years.

What is the required minimum spatial resolution of the footprints? Note that increasing the spatial resolution increases the computing time and may therefore be feasible only for a smaller domain.

19 responses

- 0.25° x 0.25°
- 0.5° x 0.5°
- 1.0° x 1.0°
- even 0.1° x 0.1°
- This really depends on the scientific questions to be addressed.

How long time periods should the model simulations cover?

20 responses

- Episodes of a few days
- Several months
- Several years
- More than 10 years

Currently we focus the footprint service on recent time periods. Which time periods would be most interesting for you?

19 responses

User interaction with the footprint service

Participants have different requests regarding the requires support to analyse the model results. Half of them would prefer to download the results and run the analysis on their local computer, while the other half would prefer pre-defined analysis tools offered in a VRE with direct access to the results.

The results will be stored in the RI's repository and receive a persistent identifier which will guarantee long term accessibility. How would you like to access the results?

20 responses

How would you like to analyse the results?

20 responses

A visualization of footprints and emissions as well as concentration time series in the footprint service is appreciated. 80% would prefer notification by e-mail after completion of the run.

The results will be stored in the RI's repository and receive a persistent identifier which will guarantee long term accessibility. How would you like to access the results?

20 responses

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APPENDIX C: User survey Task 5.3

https://github.com/iagos-dc/atmo-access/blob/main/ATMO-ACCESS_survey-5.3v2%20-%20Google%20Forms.pdf